

A Novel Single Input Multi-Output Converter Fed Induction Machine Drive for Industrial Applications

M.SATISH KUMAR
M.Tech Student Scholar
Department of Electrical &
Electronics Engineering,
Aditya Engineering College,
Tekkali;
Srikakulam (Dt); A.P, India

I.RAMESH
Assistant Professor
Department of Electrical &
Electronics Engineering,
Aditya Engineering College,
Tekkali;
Srikakulam (Dt); A.P, India

Dr.D. VIJAY KUMAR
Professor, Head of the Department
Department of Electrical &
Electronics Engineering,
AITAM Engineering College,
TEKKALI;
SRIKAKULAM (Dt); A.P, India

Abstract—Large electric drives and utility applications require advanced power electronics converter to meet the high power demands. As a result, power converter structure has been introduced as an alternative in high power and medium voltage situations. The technique of zero voltage switching in modern power conversion is explored. Several ZVS topologies and applications, limitations of the ZVS technique, and a generalized design procedure are featured. A full-bridge dc-dc converter is proposed featuring zero-voltage-switching (ZVS) of active switches over the entire conversion range. In contrast to conventional techniques the stored energy in the auxiliary inductor of the proposed converter is minimal under full load condition and it progressively increases as the load current decreases. A multi angle phase-shift modulation method is proposed which simultaneously achieves bidirectional power control, power sharing, and ZVS of all the electronic devices over the full power range without the need for auxiliary switches.

Index Terms—Bidirectional dc/dc converters, resonant conversion, zero voltage switching (ZVS).

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, dc-to-dc converter circuits employ pulse-width-modulated signal are widely [1]-[6], researched in high power conversion applications. In all the pulse-width-modulated dc-to-dc, the controllable switches are operated in a switch mode where they are required to turn on and turn off the entire load current during each switching. In this switch-mode operation, the switches are subjected to high switching stress [7], and high switching power loss that increase linearly with the switching frequency of PWM. Another significant drawback of the switch-mode operation is the EMI produced due to large di/dt and dv/dt caused by a switch-mode operation.

These shortcomings of switch-mode converters are exacerbated if the switching frequency is increased in order to reduce the converter size and weight and hence to increase the power density. Therefore, to realize high switching frequency in converter, the aforementioned shortcomings are minimized if each switch in a converter changes its status (from on to off of vice versa) when the voltage across it and/or the

current through it is zero at the switching instant. The converter topologies and the switching strategies, which results in zero-voltage and/or zero-current switching can be implementing. ZVS condition in the switch can be realized by the switch parasitic capacitance or by a resonant capacitor C_R is added in parallel across the controlled semiconductor switch as shown in the Fig. 1.

Fig1: An elementary resonant switch for achieving ZVS.

When the switch is in the on state, the capacitor is having the voltage equivalent to the forward voltage of the switch. At the time of the transition of switch state, since the voltage across the capacitor cannot change instantaneously, therefore the capacitor charging rate is decreased and hence the current almost falls to zero (0 state current) till not the voltage across the switch starts increasing to that of the 0 state value. Hence a very low power is dissipated during switching turn on operation.

The ZVS turn on is obtained by the resonance operation of the CR with an external inductor connected with the switch either in parallel or series depending up on the circuit topology. Because the resonance transition, the current starts increasing after the voltage drops down to zero and the hence ZVS is established. During resonance transition, since the current through the inductor cannot change instantly, therefore the charging rate of the inductor is reduced and the voltage decreases appreciably before the current across the switch starts rising. Thus ZVS is realized. The output parasitic capacitance of the semiconductor switching devices itself can be used for